

Investigation of the Life Skills of Young Football Players Participating in Football Trainings

“Futbol Antrenmanlarına Katılan Genç Futbolcuların Yaşam Becerilerinin İncelenmesi”

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ABSTRACT

Aim: Life skills help young people manage their lives and adapt to different life events. Therefore, young people need to have a wide range of life skills to be successful. This study was conducted to examine the life skills of individuals participating in football training in football teams in terms of various variables.

Material and Method: For this purpose, “Life Skills Scale for Sport (LSSS)” was used. The scanning method was used in the research. The research population consists of 616 athletes (aged 13-18) who play licensed football in the infrastructure of professional and amateur football teams in Istanbul in the 2022-2023 football season. The data obtained in the study was analyzed with the SPSS 25 package program. Before statistical analysis, kurtosis and skewness coefficients were examined to determine whether the distribution of the data was normal. Levene test was also performed for homogeneity of variances. In pairwise comparisons of independent variables of parametric data, t-test (independent sample), and comparisons of more than two groups were tested with one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). Tukey test was used as a post-hoc test to determine the source of the difference between groups. The statistical significance level of the results was accepted as $p < 0.05$.

Results: Significant differences were determined in many sub-dimensions such as time management, communication, goal setting, team work, social skills and emotional skills, and findings were obtained that it improved life skills.

Conclusions: As a result, preschool and school-age life skills acquired at an early age provide preparation for later adulthood. Improving life skills by devoting more time to sports activities so that individuals can meet their physical and mental needs during their youth can help them cope with the situations they encounter both physically and psychologically.

Keywords: Sports, Life Skills, Sports Activities, Education, Young Football Players

ÖZET

Amaç: Yaşam becerileri, gençlerin yaşamlarını yönetmelerine ve farklı yaşam olaylarına uyum sağlamalarına yardımcı olur. Bu nedenle, gençlerin başarılı olabilmeleri için çok çeşitli yaşam becerilerine sahip olmaları gerekmektedir. Bu çalışma, futbol takımlarında futbol antrenmanlarına katılan bireylerin yaşam becerilerinin çeşitli değişkenler açısından incelenmesi amacıyla yapılmıştır.

Materyal ve Metod: Bu amaçla “Sporun Yaşam Becerilerine Etkisi Ölçeği” kullanılmıştır. Araştırmada tarama yönteminden yararlanılmıştır. Araştırma evrenini 2022-2023 futbol sezonunda İstanbul ilindeki profesyonel ve amatör futbol takımların alt yapılarında lisanslı olarak futbol oynayan (13-18 yaş arası) 616 sporcuyu oluşturmaktadır. Araştırmada elde edilen veriler SPSS 25 paket programıyla analiz edilmiştir. İstatistiksel analiz öncesinde verilerin dağılımının normal olup olmadığını belirlemek amacıyla basıklık ve çarpıklık katsayıları incelenmiştir. Varyansların homojenliği için Levene testi de yapılmıştır. Parametrik verilerin bağımsız değişkenlerinin ikili karşılaştırılmasında t testi (bağımsız örneklem) ve ikiden fazla grubun karşılaştırılması tek yönlü varyans analizi (ANOVA) ile test edilmiştir. Gruplar arasındaki farkın kaynağını belirlemek amacıyla post-hoc test olarak Tukey testi kullanıldı. Sonuçların istatistiksel anlamlılık düzeyi $p < 0,05$ olarak kabul edildi.

Bulgular: Zaman yönetimi, iletişim, amaç belirleme, takım çalışması, sosyal beceriler ve duygusal beceriler gibi birçok alt boyutta anlamlı farklılık belirlenmiştir ve yaşam becerisini geliştirdiğine dair bulgular elde edilmiştir.

Sonuç: Sonuç olarak, erken yaşlarda edinilen okul öncesi ve okul çağındaki yaşam becerileri, ilerleyen yetişkinlik dönemleri için bir hazırlık sağlar. Gençlik döneminde bireylerin fiziksel ve zihinsel ihtiyaçlarını karşılayabilmeleri için spor faaliyetlerine daha fazla zaman ayırarak yaşam becerilerini geliştirmek hem bedensel hem de psikolojik açıdan karşılaştıkları durumlarla başa çıkmalarına yardımcı olabilir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Spor, Yaşam Becerileri, Futbol, Eğitim, Genç Futbolcu

INTRODUCTION

Sports encompass both physical activity and exercise, but they entail a set of movements governed by specific rules or objectives aimed at enhancing and excelling in certain athletic abilities. Additionally, sports foster not only functional skills but also traits such as leadership, teamwork, and socialization. They aid in the development of character in young individuals and instill behavioral habits such as motivation, discipline, perseverance, competitiveness, responsibility, confidence, and self-esteem (Pfeifer & Cornelissen, 2010; Zourikian, Jarock & Mulder, 2012).

Skills are defined as the physical, mental and behavioral capabilities that individuals require and can be acquired, honed and adjusted either individually or collectively (Cronin & Allen, 2017). Within the realm of preventive and protective research, life skills are described in scientific literature as the competencies necessary for young individuals to effectively navigate their lives (Kolburan & Tosun, 2011).

Life skills encompass behavioral, cognitive, social and intrapersonal competencies that empower individuals to achieve success across diverse contexts (Danish, Forneris, Hodge & Heke, 2004). To thrive in our rapidly evolving and dynamic contemporary society, it is essential for young individuals to possess a range of life skills (Gould, 2012). Although life skills do not directly affect academic success (Humphrey, Kalambouka, Wigelsworth, Lendrum, Deighton & Wolpert, 2011), sports and physical performance (Burton, Naylor & Holliday, 2001), general health status (Claessens, VanEerde, Rutte & Roe, 2007), mental health (Judge, Bono, Erez & Locke, 2005) and many other conditions, it plays an important role in people's lives. In addition, better managing the difficulties of adolescence and acquiring effective life skills that they can use in various areas of life can help them have a healthy and successful adolescence by preventing the formation of bad habits (Botvin & Griffin, 2004).

Researches show that young individuals enhance their life skills through extracurricular pursuits like music, drama and sports. Among these activities, sports yield the most significant array of beneficial outcomes. Specifically, it has been proposed that the interactive, emotional and social dimensions of sports render it an auspicious setting for the growth and development of young people (Kurak & Aak, 2019). In particular, research on the impact of sports on young people has shown that young people can improve their teamwork (Holt, 2007), goal setting, taking initiative and respecting other people (Holt, Tink, Mandigo & Fox, 2008), time management, cognitive and emotional skills, communication skills, and other skills. It reveals positive developments in many life skills such as social skills, leadership, problem solving and decision making. It is stated that sports for children and young people have health benefits in their future lives by reducing the risk of developing depression and depressive symptoms, as well as increasing lifelong well-being (Malm, Jakobsson & Isaksson, 2019).

Life skills are defined as "skills that enable individuals to be successful in the different environments they live in, such as school, home and neighborhood". Life skills include topics such as behavioral (communicating with peers and adults), cognitive (making effective decisions), interpersonal (being assertive) and intrapersonal (goal setting). (Danish, Forneris, Hodge & Heke, 2004).

Life skills develop skills in adolescents to both build the competencies necessary for human development and to adopt positive behaviors that enable them to effectively cope with the challenges of daily life. It states that developing life skills can delay the onset of drug use, prevent high-risk sexual behavior, teach anger management, improve academic performance, and promote positive social attitudes (Mangrulkar et. al., 2001).

As stated by WHO (1999), psycho-social skills and abilities can be applied to the development of target qualities such as self-confidence and socialization among life skills, and their importance in preparing young people for adulthood and supporting their healthy development is emphasized.

The development of life skills is especially vital for young individuals, encompassing the achievement of core objectives in the trajectory of human maturation and advancement. The indispensable life skills essential for fostering the robust and superior development of youth, along with strategies for their nurture, persist as topics of continual discourse within modern societies. Consequently, it is emphasized that educational programs should incorporate life skills as an integral element. These skills empower young individuals to effectively manage their lives and adapt to various life circumstances (Gazda & Brooks, 1985; Larson & Cook, 1985)

For this reason, young people need to have many different life skills in order to adapt to the competitive and constantly changing living conditions of the age and to be successful (Gould & Carson, 2010). Life skills indirectly include academic success (Humphrey et al., 2011), sports and exercise performance (Burton et al., 2001), general health (Claessens et al., 2007), psychological well-being (Judge et al., 2005). It is an important determining factor in an individual's life, as it is associated with many situations such as workplace productivity and success (Rubin & Morreale, 1996). In addition, when the life skills required to cope with the difficulties of adolescence can be transferred to different life areas, they can ensure healthy development and success, for example, by keeping young people away from harmful habits such as alcohol and drug use (Botvin & Griffin, 2004).

Interest in developing life skills through sport in children and young people is clearly present today, with most contemporary youth sport organizations considering social-emotional development as one of their primary goals (Gould & Carson, 2008).

Therefore, it is clear that more research is needed on this topic. In this context, the study aims to examine how it affects the life skills of young football players who participate in football training. According to the survey results, the life skills of the students who do sports were investigated in the light of some demographic information.

Considering that it is different from the studies in the literature, the main purpose of this study was determined to examine the life skills of young football players participating in football training in terms of various variables. For this purpose, answers were sought to the following questions:

1- There is a statistically significant difference in the acquisition of life skills by young football players according to gender.

2- There is a statistically significant difference in football players' acquisition of life skills depending on whether they play continuously in the team.

3- There is a statistically significant difference in football players' acquisition of life skills according to the year of playing football.

4- There is a significant difference in gaining life skills depending on the settlement where football players spend most of their lives.

5- There is a significant difference in football players' acquisition of life skills according to the education level of the mother.

6- There is a significant difference in football players' acquisition of life skills according to the education level of the father.

7- There is a significant difference in the acquisition of life skills by athletes with high family income.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

This study was conducted using screening methods. The survey method refers to studies that aim to collect data in order to define the characteristics of a specific group (Büyüköztürk, Kılıç Çakmak, Akgün, Karadeniz & Demirel, 2014). The scanning method aims to portray a past or present situation as it is. It is attempted to describe the event, individuals, objects or conditions on which the research focuses, as it is and in its real state (Karasar, 2009).

Research Group

The research population consists of 616 athletes (aged 13-18) who play licensed football in the infrastructure of professional and amateur football teams in Istanbul in the 2022-2023 football season.

Convenience sampling is defined as a sample consisting of individuals who are in the immediate vicinity, easily reachable and willing to participate in the research voluntarily (Ekiz, 2009).

Data Collection Tools

In addition to the personal information form, individuals who wanted to participate in the research were given the survey form, which included life skills scale statements, over the internet (Google Forms) and were asked to answer the statements in this form sincerely (Annex 1). The scale, whose original form is the Life Skills Scale for Sports (LSSS), was developed as a 5-point Likert type by Cronin and Allen in 2017 to evaluate life skills gained through sports (Cronin & Allen, 2017). The scale can be applied to secondary school, high school and university students up to the age of 21. The Turkish validity and reliability of the scale (Açak & Düz, 2018) consists of a total of 30 items from 7 sub-dimensions, including teamwork. It consists of goal setting, time management, emotional skills, communication, social skills and leadership sub-dimensions. Each statement in the scale is scored on a 5-point Likert scale, including "Totally Disagree (1)" and "Totally Agree (5)". There are no reverse scored statements in the scale.

Data Analysis

Following the Ethics Committee Report, after obtaining the necessary permission from the Istanbul Amateur Sports Clubs Federation (IASKF), the football players who were licensed and volunteered in the football clubs and the athletes whose consent was obtained by the parents of these football players were filled in the measurement tools on the internet (Google Forms). After the survey application phase was completed, data entry and database preparation were carried out. The data obtained in the study was analyzed with the SPSS 25 package program. Before statistical analysis, kurtosis and skewness coefficients were examined to determine whether the distribution of the data was normal. It was observed that the values were between (-1) and (+1) and were normally distributed (Hair, Black, Babin, Anderson & Tatham, 2013). Levene test was also performed for homogeneity of variances. In pairwise comparisons of independent variables of parametric data, t-test (independent sample) and comparisons of more than two groups were tested with one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). Tukey test was used as a post-hoc test to determine the source of the difference between groups. The statistical significance level of the results was accepted as $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

Table 1. Comparison of Life Skills of the Research Group According to Gender Variable

Variable	Group	n	X	Sd	t	p
Time Management	Male	563	3.79	0.67	2.47	.014*
	Female	53	3.55	0.78		
Communication	Male	563	3.96	0.62	2.24	.025*
	Female	53	3.75	0.70		
Leadership	Male	563	3.89	0.65	0.51	0.60
	Female	53	3.84	0.65		
Team work	Male	563	4.07	0.55	0.72	0.47
	Female	53	4.01	0.56		
Social Skills	Male	563	3.86	0.71	1.75	0.08
	Female	53	3.68	0.76		
Emotional Skills	Male	563	3.83	0.75	1.55	0.12
	Female	53	3.66	0.87		
Goal Setting	Male	563	4.28	0.63	2.54	.011*
	Female	53	4.04	0.84		

* p<.05

According to Table 1, depending on the gender variable, it was determined that the difference in time management, communication and goal setting sub-dimensions of life skills was statistically significant in favor of men.

Table 2. Comparison of Life Skills of the Research Group According to Team Playing Status Variable

Variable	Group	n	X	Sd	t	p
Time Management	I'm playing for the team's first eleven	563	3.82	0.68	2.20	.028*
	Entering the the game from the bench.	53	3.69	0.69		
Communication	I'm playing for the team's first eleven	563	3.96	0.64	1.07	.282
	Entering the the game from the bench.	53	3.91	0.61		
Leadership	I'm playing for the team's first eleven	563	3.96	0.61	3.74	.000*
	Entering the the game from the bench.	53	3.76	0.70		
Team work	I'm playing for the team's first eleven	563	4.13	0.52	3.81	.000*
	Entering the the game from the bench.	53	3.96	0.59		
Social Skills	I'm playing for the team's first eleven	563	3.90	0.69	2.49	.013*
	Entering the the game from the bench.	53	3.75	0.73		
Emotional Skills	I'm playing for the team's first eleven	563	3.88	0.75	2.50	.012*
	Entering the the game from the bench.	53	3.72	0.77		
Goal Setting	I'm playing for the team's first eleven	563	4.35	0.60	4.49	.000*
	Entering the the game from the bench.	53	4.11	0.71		

* p<.05

According to Table 2, depending on the team playing status variable, it was determined that the difference in the time management, leadership, teamwork, social skills, emotional skills and goal setting sub-dimensions of life skills was statistically significant in favor of the athletes who played for the team's first eleven.

Table 3. Comparison of Life Skills of the Research Group According to the Year of Doing Sports

Variable	Group	n	X	Sd	F	p	Tukey
Time Management	0-1 Year (a)	29	3.85	0.62	6,745	.000*	b < d
	2-3 Years (b)	70	3.49	0.75			
	4-5 Years (c)	148	3.70	0.63			
	more than 6 years (d)	369	3.86	0.69			
Communication	0-1 Year (a)	29	3.97	0.61	0.074	.974	-
	2-3 Years (b)	70	3.96	0.68			
	4-5 Years (c)	148	3.93	0.59			
	more than 6 years (d)	369	3.95	0.65			
Leadership	0-1 Year (a)	29	3.96	0.61	1.347	.258	-
	2-3 Years (b)	70	3.81	0.73			
	4-5 Years (c)	148	3.83	0.65			
	more than 6 years (d)	369	3.93	0.65			
Team work	0-1 Year (a)	29	3.97	0.57	4.394	.005*	b < d
	2-3 Years (b)	70	3.88	0.62			
	4-5 Years (c)	148	4.05	0.51			
	more than 6 years (d)	369	4.13	0.55			
Social Skills	0-1 Year (a)	29	3.96	0.64	1.009	.388	-
	2-3 Years (b)	70	3.80	0.83			
	4-5 Years (c)	148	3.79	0.74			
	more than 6 years (d)	369	3.88	0.69			
Emotional Skills	0-1 Year (a)	29	3.88	0.76	1.443	.229	-
	2-3 Years (b)	70	3.66	0.88			
	4-5 Years (c)	148	3.79	0.75			
	more than 6 years (d)	369	3.86	0.75			
Goal Setting	0-1 Year (a)	29	4.17	0.64	0.001	.001*	b < d
	2-3 Years (b)	70	4.00	0.82			
	4-5 Years (c)	148	4.25	0.59			
	more than 6 years (d)	369	4.33	0.64			

* p<.05

According to Table 3, there is a significant difference in the time management, teamwork and goal setting scores of the study group depending on the variable of the year of doing sports. Tukey test was used as a post-hoc test to determine the source of the difference. As a result of the test, the time management, teamwork and goal setting average of football players with 2-3 years of experience is significantly lower than the average of those with more than 6 (six) years of experience.

Table 4. Comparison of Life Skills of the Research Group According to Where They Spend Most of Their Lives

Variable	Group	n	X	Sd	F	p	Tukey
Time Management	Big City (a)	459	3.83	0.64	3.711	.011*	c < a
	City Center (b)	32	3.63	0.85			
	District Center (c)	113	3.61	0.80			
	Village-Town (d)	12	3.75	0.62			
Communication	Big City (a)	459	3.98	0.62	2.144	.094	-

	City Center (b)	32	3.85	0.69			
	District Center (c)	113	3.83	0.68			
	Village-Town (d)	12	3.92	0.57			
Leadership	Big City (a)	459	3.92	0.62	1.541	.203	-
	City Center (b)	32	3.86	0.60			
	District Center (c)	113	3.80	0.80			
	Village-Town (d)	12	3.68	0.72			
Team work	Big City (a)	459	4.11	0.52	2.486	.060	-
	City Center (b)	32	3.93	0.52			
	District Center (c)	113	3.98	0.68			
	Village-Town (d)	12	4.01	0.54			
Social Skills	Big City (a)	459	3.91	0.70	3.372	.018*	c < a
	City Center (b)	32	3.78	0.59			
	District Center (c)	113	3.67	0.78			
	Village-Town (d)	12	3.75	0.87			
Emotional Skills	Big City (a)	459	3.86	0.75	2.399	.067	-
	City Center (b)	32	3.73	0.59			
	District Center (c)	113	3.66	0.85			
	Village-Town (d)	12	3.96	0.80			
Goal Setting	Big City (a)	459	4.32	0.59	4.994	.002*	c < a
	City Center (b)	32	4.05	0.71			
	District Center (c)	113	4.10	0.83			
	Village-Town (d)	12	4.17	0.59			

* p<.05

According to Table 4, while there is no significant difference in communication (F=2.144, p>0.05), leadership (F=1.541, p>0.05), teamwork (F=2.486, p>0.05) and emotional skills (F=2.399, p>0.05) scores depending on the variable of “place of residence where they spent most of their lives”. There is a significant difference in time management (F=3,711, p<0,05), social skills (F=3,372, p<0,05) and goal setting (F=4,994, p<0,05) scores. In order to determine the source of the difference in time management, social skills and goal setting scores, Tukey test, one of the post-hoc tests, was conducted. As a result of the test, the average of time management, social skills and goal setting scores of those who spend most of their lives in the district center is significantly lower than the average of those who spend most of their lives in the big city.

Table 5. Comparison of Life Skills of the Research Group According to Mother's Educational Status

Variable	Group	n	X	Sd	F	p	Tukey
Time Management	Illiterate (a)	12	3.98	0.63	4.480	.001*	b < c, e
	Primary School-Middle School (b)	243	3.65	0.73			
	High school (c)	215	3.83	0.69			
	University (d)	128	3.84	0.58			
	Master's-PhD (e)	18	4.17	0.61			
Communication	Illiterate (a)	12	4.04	0.71	3.014	.018*	b < c
	Primary School-Middle School (b)	243	3.85	0.66			
	High school (c)	215	4.02	0.63			
	University (d)	128	3.97	0.58			
	Master's-PhD (e)	18	4.18	0.53			
Leadership	Illiterate (a)	12	3.80	0.87	1.189	.314	-
	Primary School-Middle School (b)	243	3.83	0.69			
	High school (c)	215	3.93	0.64			
	University (d)	128	3.94	0.60			

Team work	Master's-PhD (e)	18	4.04	0.63	1.493	.203	-
	Illiterate (a)	12	4.08	0.72			
	Primary School-Middle School (b)	243	4.01	0.62			
	High school (c)	215	4.12	0.49			
	University (d)	128	4.10	0.52			
	Master's-PhD (e)	18	4.16	0.52			
Social Skills	Illiterate (a)	12	3.69	0.83	2.674	.031	-
	Primary School-Middle School (b)	243	3.75	0.74			
	High school (c)	215	3.92	0.69			
	University (d)	128	3.91	0.71			
	Master's-PhD (e)	18	4.10	0.60			
	Illiterate (a)	12	3.65	1.07			
Primary School-Middle School (b)	243	3.71	0.83				
High school (c)	215	3.92	0.67				
University (d)	128	3.86	0.75				
Master's-PhD (e)	18	4.01	0.64				
Illiterate (a)	12	4.56	0.44	2.098	.08	-	
Primary School-Middle School (b)	243	4.19	0.68				
High school (c)	215	4.32	0.66				
University (d)	128	4.27	0.62				
Master's-PhD (e)	18	4.43	0.60				

* p<.05

According to Table 5, there is no significant difference in leadership ($F=1.189, p> 0.05$), teamwork ($F=1.493, p> 0.05$) and goal setting ($F=2.098, p>0.05$) scores, but there is a significant difference in time management ($F=4.480, p<0.05$), communication ($F=3.014, p<0.05$), social skills ($F=2.674, p<0.05$) and emotional skills ($F=2.787, p<0.05$) scores depending on the mother's education level. In order to determine the source of the difference in time management, communication, emotional skills and social skills scores, Tukey test, one of the post-hoc tests, was conducted. As a result of the test, the mean time management, communication and emotional skills scores of those whose mother's educational status was primary-secondary school were significantly lower than those of those whose mother's educational status was high school and master's-doctorate. Although there was a significant difference in the social skills sub-dimension scores ($F=2.674, p<0.05$), no difference was found between the groups in the Tukey test conducted to determine the difference between the groups.

Table 6. Comparison of Life Skills of the Research Group According to Father's Educational Status

Variable	Group	n	X	Sd	F	p	Tukey
Time Management	Illiterate (a)	7	3.75	0.43	2.955	.020*	-
	Primary School-Middle School (b)	225	3.71	0.73			
	High school (c)	236	3.74	0.65			
	University (d)	123	3.91	0.67			
	Master's-PhD (e)	25	4.06	0.60			
	Illiterate (a)	7	3.89	0.45			
Primary School-Middle School (b)	225	3.92	0.70				
High school (c)	236	3.92	0.62				
University (d)	123	4.00	0.54				
Master's-PhD (e)	25	4.08	0.62				
Illiterate (a)	7	4.20	0.59	1.369	.243	-	
Primary School-Middle School (b)	225	3.89	0.71				
High school (c)	236	3.85	0.64				
University (d)	123	3.94	0.60				

Team work	Master's-PhD (e)	25	4.09	0.54	0.620	.649	-
	Illiterate (a)	7	4.14	0.57			
	Primary School-Middle School (b)	225	4.05	0.62			
	High school (c)	236	4.06	0.51			
	University (d)	123	4.11	0.54			
Social Skills	Master's-PhD (e)	25	4.20	0.43	0.973	.422	-
	Illiterate (a)	7	3.82	0.62			
	Primary School-Middle School (b)	225	3.88	0.75			
	High school (c)	236	3.80	0.70			
	University (d)	123	3.88	0.70			
Emotional Skills	Master's-PhD (e)	25	4.05	0.64	1.091	.360	-
	Illiterate (a)	7	3.57	0.81			
	Primary School-Middle School (b)	225	3.79	0.83			
	High school (c)	236	3.81	0.70			
	University (d)	123	3.86	0.78			
Goal Setting	Master's-PhD (e)	25	4.08	0.73	0.227	.923	-
	Illiterate (a)	7	4.36	0.43			
	Primary School-Middle School (b)	225	4.28	0.66			
	High school (c)	236	4.24	0.66			
	University (d)	123	4.26	0.68			
	Master's-PhD (e)	25	4.35	0.56			

* p<.05

According to Table 6, no significant difference was found in communication (F=0.684, p>0.05), leadership (F=1.369, p>0.05), teamwork (F=0.620, p>0.05), social skills (F=0.973, p>0.05), emotional skills (F=1.091, p>0.05) and goal setting (F=0.227, p>0.05) scores depending on the father's education level. Although there was a significant difference in time management (F=2,955, p<0,05) scores according to the father's education level, no difference was found between the groups in the Tukey test, one of the post-hoc tests conducted to determine the difference between the groups.

Table 7. Comparison of Life Skills of the Research Group According to Family Attitudes

Variable	Group	n	X	Sd	F	p	Tukey
Time Management	Democratic (a)	188	3.89	0.73	5.691	.001*	d < a, c
	Authoritarian (b)	84	3.67	0.55			
	Protective (c)	329	3.76	0.67			
	Irrelevant (d)	15	3.22	0.97			
Communication	Democratic (a)	188	4.03	0.65	3.071	.027*	d < a
	Authoritarian (b)	84	3.90	0.60			
	Protective (c)	329	3.93	0.60			
	Irrelevant (d)	15	3.57	1.08			
Leadership	Democratic (a)	188	3.93	0.69	1.292	.276	-
	Authoritarian (b)	84	3.81	0.60			
	Protective (c)	329	3.90	0.64			
	Irrelevant (d)	15	3.67	0.89			
Team work	Democratic (a)	188	4.12	0.54	1.413	.238	-
	Authoritarian (b)	84	4.10	0.49			
	Protective (c)	329	4.05	0.55			
	Irrelevant (d)	15	3.87	1.00			
Social Skills	Democratic (a)	188	3.98	0.74	5.042	.002*	d < a, c
	Authoritarian (b)	84	3.81	0.68			
	Protective (c)	329	3.82	0.68			

Emotional Skills	Irrelevant (d)	15	3.33	1.05	2.985	.031*	d < a
	Democratic (a)	188	3.92	0.72			
	Authoritarian (b)	84	3.78	0.73			
	Protective (c)	329	3.79	0.78			
	Irrelevant (d)	15	3.38	1.13			
Goal Setting	Democratic (a)	188	4.31	0.67	2.177	.09	-
	Authoritarian (b)	84	4.21	0.61			
	Protective (c)	329	4.28	0.64			
	Irrelevant (d)	15	3.88	0.96			

* p<.05

According to Table 7, although there was no significant difference in leadership (F=1,292, p>0,05), teamwork (F=1,413, p>0,05) and goal setting (F=2,177, p>0,05) scores depending on the variable of family attitude towards the athlete, there is a significant difference in time management (F=5,691, p<0,05), communication (F=3,071, p<0,05), social skills (F=5,1042, p<0,05) and emotional skills (F=2,985, p<0,05) scores. In the Tukey test conducted to determine the source of the difference in time management, communication, social skills and emotional skills scores, the mean scores of communication and emotional skills of those with indifferent family attitudes were significantly lower than the mean scores of those with democratic family attitudes. The mean scores of time management and social skills of those with indifferent family attitudes were significantly lower than the mean scores of those with democratic and protective family attitudes.

Table 8. Comparison of Life Skills of the Research Group According to Coach Attitude

Variable	Group	n	X	Sd	F	p
Time Management	Democratic	267	3.78	0.70	0.790	.500
	Authoritarian	165	3.72	0.66		
	Protector	171	3.83	0.69		
	Irrelevant	13	3.69	0.78		
Communication	Democratic	267	3.91	0.69	1.402	.241
	Authoritarian	165	3.92	0.59		
	Protector	171	4.03	0.57		
	Irrelevant	13	3.87	0.76		
Leadership	Democratic	267	3.89	0.67	0.982	.401
	Authoritarian	165	3.85	0.66		
	Protector	171	3.95	0.60		
	Irrelevant	13	3.71	0.91		
Team work	Democratic	267	4.08	0.57	1.103	.347
	Authoritarian	165	4.07	0.52		
	Protector	171	4.08	0.56		
	Irrelevant	13	3.79	0.72		
Social Skills	Democratic	267	3.87	0.75	0.308	.820
	Authoritarian	165	3.81	0.67		
	Protector	171	3.87	0.73		
	Irrelevant	13	3.87	0.65		
Emotional Skills	Democratic	267	3.80	0.80	0.185	.907
	Authoritarian	165	3.85	0.72		
	Protector	171	3.82	0.77		
	Irrelevant	13	3.88	0.67		
Goal Setting	Democratic	267	4.24	0.70	0.947	.417
	Authoritarian	165	4.24	0.63		
	Protector	171	4.34	0.61		
	Irrelevant	13	4.23	0.62		

According to Table 8, depending on the variable of the coach's attitude towards the athlete, no significant difference was found in time management ($F=0.790, p>0.05$), communication ($F=1.402, p>0.05$), leadership ($F=0.982, p>0.05$), teamwork ($F=1.103, p>0.05$), social skills ($F=0.308, p>0.05$), emotional skills ($F=0.185, p>0.05$) and goal setting ($F=0.947, p>0.05$) scores.

Table 9. Comparison of Life Skills of the Research Group According to Family Income Status

Variable	Group	n	X	Sd	F	p	Tukey
Time Management	5000-10000 TL	137	3.65	0.73	2.796	.039*	-
	10001-20000 TL	249	3.76	0.69			
	20001-30000	120	3.87	0.63			
	over 30000 TL	110	3.85	0.67			
Communication	5000-10000 TL	137	3.92	0.69	0.283	.838	-
	10001-20000 TL	249	3.94	0.59			
	20001-30000	120	3.97	0.62			
	over 30000 TL	110	3.98	0.68			
Leadership	5000-10000 TL	137	3.76	0.71	2.621	.050	-
	10001-20000 TL	249	3.92	0.63			
	20001-30000	120	3.97	0.61			
	over 30000 TL	110	3.92	0.67			
Team work	5000-10000 TL	137	4.03	0.62	0.589	.622	-
	10001-20000 TL	249	4.07	0.54			
	20001-30000	120	4.07	0.55			
	over 30000 TL	110	4.12	0.51			
Social Skills	5000-10000 TL	137	3.74	0.73	2.038	.107	-
	10001-20000 TL	249	3.85	0.72			
	20001-30000	120	3.92	0.68			
	over 30000 TL	110	3.94	0.71			
Emotional Skills	5000-10000 TL	137	3.76	0.82	0.604	.612	-
	10001-20000 TL	249	3.81	0.78			
	20001-30000	120	3.87	0.71			
	over 30000 TL	110	3.86	0.74			
Goal Setting	5000-10000 TL	137	4.17	0.74	1.470	.222	-
	10001-20000 TL	249	4.27	0.63			
	20001-30000	120	4.31	0.60			
	over 30000 TL	110	4.32	0.66			

* $p<.05$

According to Table 9, there is no significant difference in communication ($F=0,283, p>0,05$), leadership ($F=2,621, p>0,05$), teamwork ($F=0,589, p>0,05$), social skills ($F=2,038, p>0,05$), emotional skills ($F=0,604, p>0,05$) and goal setting ($F=1,470, p>0,05$) scores depending on family income status. Although there was a significant difference in time management ($F=2,796, p<0,05$) scores according to family income status, no difference was found between the groups in the Tukey test, one of the post-hoc tests conducted to determine the difference between the groups.

Table 10. Comparison of Life Skills According to the Age Category of the Research Group

Variable	Group	n	X	Sd	F	p	Tukey
Time Management	U13(a)	156	3.69	0.61	1.803	.110	-
	U14(b)	89	3.88	0.53			
	U15(c)	139	3.75	0.65			

	U16(d)	37	3.96	0.65			
	U17(e)	169	3.75	0.82			
	U18(f)	26	3.94	0.85			
Communication	U13(a)	156	4.02	0.56	1.552	.172	-
	U14(b)	89	3.99	0.66			
	U15(c)	139	3.85	0.63			
	U16(d)	37	3.85	0.65			
	U17(e)	169	3.97	0.64			
	U18(f)	26	3.87	0.87			
Leadership	U13(a)	156	3.93	0.60	2.281	0.045*	d < b
	U14(b)	89	3.99	0.65			
	U15(c)	139	3.92	0.63			
	U16(d)	37	3.61	0.81			
	U17(e)	169	3.84	0.67			
	U18(f)	26	3.95	0.66			
Team work	U13(a)	156	4.07	0.53	0.641	.668	-
	U14(b)	89	4.09	0.49			
	U15(c)	139	4.09	0.52			
	U16(d)	37	4.00	0.65			
	U17(e)	169	4.04	0.61			
	U18(f)	26	4.22	0.58			
Social Skills	U13(a)	156	3.88	0.72	1.071	.375	-
	U14(b)	89	3.88	0.77			
	U15(c)	139	3.82	0.65			
	U16(d)	37	3.74	0.79			
	U17(e)	169	3.83	0.73			
	U18(f)	26	4.12	0.66			
Emotional Skills	U13(a)	156	3.79	0.72	1.241	.288	-
	U14(b)	89	3.93	0.71			
	U15(c)	139	3.71	0.79			
	U16(d)	37	3.93	0.82			
	U17(e)	169	3.83	0.80			
	U18(f)	26	3.95	0.74			
Goal Setting	U13(a)	156	4.21	0.70	1.065	.379	-
	U14(b)	89	4.36	0.57			
	U15(c)	139	4.29	0.61			
	U16(d)	37	4.34	0.65			
	U17(e)	169	4.22	0.72			
	U18(f)	26	4.39	0.50			

* p<.05

According to Table 10, there is no significant difference in time management (F=1,803, p>0,05), communication (F=1,552, p>0,05), teamwork (F=0,641, p>0,05), social skills (F=1,071, p>0,05), emotional skills (F=1,241, p>0,05) and goal setting (F=1,065, p>0,05) scores depending on the age category in which they play football. There is a significant difference in leadership (F=2,281, p<0,05) scores according to the category of soccer played. In the Tukey test, which is one of the post-hoc tests to determine the difference between the groups, the leadership scores of those playing in the U16 category are significantly lower than those playing in the U14 category.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The purpose of this study was to investigate the life skills of young football players engaged in football training across different factors.

Regarding the variable of gender, a significant difference favoring males was observed in the life skills dimensions of time management, communication and goal setting. This finding aligns with the research conducted by Altun et al. (2021) in the central area of Istanbul. Upon reviewing other literature, it becomes evident that female students engaged in sports exhibit more advanced emotional and social skills, with sports having a positive impact on girls' life skills. In contrast to the outcomes of this study, several other studies (Kasatura, 1991; Avşar & Öztürk, 2007; Seven, 2008; Kabakçı and Fidan, 2008; Kurak and Açak, 2019; Düz & Aslan, 2020) indicate that girls possess greater life skills than boys and demonstrate superior communication abilities.

In our study, it was determined that the years of doing sports and the sub-dimensions of life skills such as time management, teamwork and goal setting positively affected the athletes by doing sports for more than six years. This result coincides with the study conducted by Düz and Aslan (2020) in Mersin city center. In the research conducted by Düz and Arslan (2020), it was observed that there was a significant difference in time management and goal setting among those who have been doing sports for 8 years or more. In another study conducted by Kurak and Açak (2019), a significant difference was observed in the time management, communication, leadership, teamwork and social skills scores of those who have been doing sports for 6 years or more.

No statistically significant difference was found in the life skills sub-dimensions according to the family income variable. In studies parallel to our study, it is seen that the income level of the family does not have a high impact on the life skills of young people (Mayer and Salovey, 1997; Türk, 2015; Taşçı, 2020; Altun et al., 2021). There are studies in the literature that are opposite to our study. Contrary to our study, time management, communication, leadership, teamwork, social skills and emotional skill scores of those with higher income levels were found to be statistically significant compared to those with lower family income. (Kardağ, 2019; Zeze & Erel, 2021).

Statistically significant differences were detected in the life skills sub-dimensions of time management, communication and emotional skills scores of the participants, depending on their mother's education level, at primary school-middle school, high school and graduate -doctoral levels. It has been observed that the differences increase as the education level of the mother increases. In other studies parallel to our study, significant differences were found in the communication skills level of students who do sports according to the variable of family education level. As the level of education increases, the same parallelism appears in gaining life skills and high scores are seen in all sub-dimensions (Çağlayan, 2004; Ulukan, 2012; Altun et al., 2021; Sarı, 2021).

The life skills subscale scores of the participants did not show any significant difference based on their fathers' level of education. This outcome aligns with the findings of the research conducted by Altun et al. (2021) in the central area of Istanbul.

When we examined life skills according to the family attitude variable, statistically significant differences were detected in time management, communication, social skills and emotional skills sub-dimension scores in favor of families whose family attitude towards the athlete was democratic. against athlete It is seen that the life skills of those whose family attitudes are democratic and protective are higher than those of families whose family attitudes are indifferent. This result coincides with Wang et al.'s (2021)

research on high school athletes. It has been determined that positive parental attitudes positively affect life skills.

In our study, no significant difference was found in life skills subscale scores according to the coach attitude variable. Contrary to our study, it is stated that the positive attitude of the coach has a positive effect on the athletes' acquisition of life skills (Flett et al., 2013; Cronin & Allen, 2018).

Significant differences were detected in time management, social skills and goal setting sub-dimensions depending on the variable of residence where he spent most of his life. Life skill gains are higher in favor of athletes who spend most of their lives in big cities. It makes us think that athletes who grow up in big cities can gain life skills more easily by being able to access the social, cultural and sports opportunities they want more easily.

When we examined life skills according to the variable of playing in a team, a significant difference was found in the subscale scores of time management, leadership, teamwork, social skills, emotional skills and goal setting. The total score points of the athletes who started the matches as the starting 11 are significantly higher than the athletes who started the match as substitutes. This result is parallel to the research conducted by Toros (2005) with young basketball players. It has been observed that increasing the time spent in the game positively affects life satisfaction.

When we look at the literature, we see that sports affect young people on teamwork (Holt, 2007), goal setting, taking proactive steps, respecting others (Holt, Tink, Mandigo & Fox 2008), effective time management (Fraser-Thomas and Côté, 2009), cognitive skills (Danish, Forneris, Hodge, & Heke, 2004), motional competencies (Brunelle, Danish & Forneris 2007), communication abilities (Gould, Collins, Lauer & Chung, 2007), social abilities (Gould, Flett & Lauer 2012) and leadership qualities (Camiré, Trudel and Forneris 2012) appears to have a positive impact. This information also supports our study.

Based on the research results, the following recommendations can be made:

During youth, individuals spend more time on sports activities to meet both their physical and mental needs and develop their life skills, which can help them cope with the difficulties they face both physically and psychologically.

Pre-school and school-age life skills acquired at an early age constitute a preparation for later adulthood and the importance of sports in acquiring these skills and the increase in research in this field will contribute to a better understanding of this subject. Therefore, developing life skills during childhood and adolescence is of great importance in terms of preparation for pre-adulthood. For this reason, students who are successful in physical education courses should be directed to sports clubs.

Situations such as starting sports-related experiences at an early age, taking part in school or club teams and working with different coaches will contribute to the life skills of young people. Therefore, it is recommended that young people engage in sports at an early age to improve their life skills. For this reason, school teams, school sports clubs, neighborhood teams and youth teams of clubs should be supported or encouraged.

Families who want their children to be best prepared for the future and life can be advised to encourage their children by directing them to sports and support them in this direction, with the awareness that sports help to acquire and develop many life skills.

Through youth sports activities; by supporting their healthy physical and mental development, they should be ensured to take part in society as healthy individuals.

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